

Effect of ageing and time since first heroin and cocaine use on mortality from external and natural causes in a Spanish cohort of drug users

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ABSTRACT

Background: We aimed to assess the effect of ageing and time since first heroin/cocaine use on causespecific mortality risk and age disparities in excess mortality among heroin (HUs) and cocaine users (CUs) in Spain.

Methods: A cohort of 15,305 HUs and 11,905 CUs aged 15–49 starting drug treatment during 1997–2007 in Madrid and Barcelona was followed until December 2008. Effects of ageing and time since first heroin/ cocaine use were estimated using a competing risk Cox model and the relative and absolute excess mortality compared to the general population through directly age-sex standardized rate ratios (SRRs) and differences (SRDs), respectively.

Results: Mortality risk from natural causes increased with time since first heroin use, whereas that from overdose declined after having peaked in the first quinquennium. Significant effects of time since first cocaine use were not identified, although fatal overdose risk seemed higher in CUs after five years. Mortality risk from natural causes (HUs and CUs), injuries (HUs), and overdoses (CUs) increased with age, the latter without reaching statistical significance. Crude mortality rates from overdoses and injuries remained very high at age 40–59 among both HUs (595 and 217 deaths/100,000 person-years, respectively) and CUs (191 and 88 deaths/100,000 person-years). SRDs from all and natural causes were much higher at age 40–59 than 15–29 in both HUs (2134 vs. 834 deaths/100,000 person-years) and CUs (927 vs. 221 deaths/100,000 person-years), while the opposite occurred with SRRs.

Conclusion: The high mortality risk among HUs and CUs at all ages from both external and natural causes, and increased SRDs with ageing, suggest that high-level healthcare and harm reduction services should be established early and maintained throughout the lifetime of these populations.

INTRODUCTION

Heroin and cocaine use disorders are chronic and relapsing diseases, which can seriously affect drug users' health for many years. In a recent meta-analysis the pooled mortality risk compared to the general population (GP) was 15 and 4–8 times higher among heroin users and cocaine users, respectively (Degenhardt, Bucello et al., 2011; Degenhardt, Singleton et al., 2011). However, the mortality risk also depends greatly on other cohort characteristics, especially drug-injecting prevalence or time in opioid substitution treatment (OST). Thus, among heroin users one meta-analysis found that mortality risk in cohorts with drug-injecting prevalence >85% was double that of those with lower prevalence (Degenhardt, Bucello et al., 2011), while another found it was triple during the period outside OST than when they were in OST (Sordo et al., 2017). Among heroin users such excess mortality is largely due to overdoses, although injuries (unintentional injuries, suicide and homicide) also contribute substantially (Degenhardt, Bucello et al., 2011; Degenhardt, Larney, Randall, Burns, & Hall, 2014; Pierce, Bird, Hickman, & Millar, 2015). In cocaine users, overdose, injuries and circulatory diseases may make an important contribution to excess mortality, although the evidence is scarce (Degenhardt, Singleton et al., 2011). Finally, in some cohorts with high drug-injecting prevalence, infectious diseases (mainly HIV) are a major cause of death (Degenhardt, Bucello et al., 2011; Degenhardt, Singleton et al., 2011).

In developed countries, problem heroin and cocaine users are getting older, and long-term users (Arndt, Clayton, & Schultz, 2011; Armstrong, 2007; Barrio et al., 2013; Degenhardt et al., 2014; EMCDDA, 2015; Wu & Blazer, 2011) are accumulating many comorbidities and increased social isolation (Darke et al., 2009; Giraudon, Vicente, Matias, Mounteney, & Griffiths, 2012; Rosen, Smith, & ReynoldsIII, 2008; Larney et al., 2015; Rosen, Hunsaker, Albert, Cornelius, & ReynoldsIII, 2011; Wu and Blazer, 2011). This could partly explain why, despite improved care (i.e., OST), their mortality risk has not declined greatly, except for HIV-related causes (EMCDDA, 2015; Giraudon et al., 2012; Hedegaard, Chen, & Warner, 2015). Quantifying changes in cause-specific mortality by age and time since first heroin/cocaine use is important to target intervention programs more accurately. However, few studies among such drug users have focused on these aspects (Degenhardt, Bucello et al., 2011; Degenhardt et al., 2014; Nambiar et al., 2015; Pierce et al., 2015), and they sometimes show inconsistent results. There is evidence that among heroin users and drug injectors, the main causes of death change with age, with external causes (overdose and injuries) predominating among younger users, and natural causes (i.e., liver disease) among older ones (Clausen, Waal, Thoresen, & Gossop, 2009; Degenhardt et al., 2014; Maxwell et al., 2005; Maxwell, Pullum, & Tannert, 2005). Moreover, it is generally accepted that fatal and non-fatal overdose occur not only among the youngest and most inexperienced opioid users, but also in older users with many years of drug use (Darke & Hall, 2003; UNODC, 2015; Warner-Smith, Darke, Lynskey, & Hall, 2001). Many studies have found that fatal overdose risk does not decrease with age (Bartu, Freeman, Gawthorne, Codde, & Holman, 2004; Bird, Hutchinson, & Goldberg, 2003; Buster, van Brussel, & van den Brink, 2002; Clausen et al., 2009; Merrall, Bird, & Hutchinson, 2012; Odegard, Amundsen, & Kielland, 2007; Pierce et al., 2015) or time since first opioid use (Odegard et al., 2007). Mortality risk from natural causes usually increases with age, especially after age 50 (Brugal et al., 2005; Clausen et al., 2009; EMCDDA, 2015; Larney et al., 2015; Pierce et al., 2015), the same as in the GP, whereas fatal-injury risk shows inconsistent results between studies, with increases (Clausen et al., 2009), stability (Larney et al., 2015; Pierce et al., 2015), and decreases (Copeland, Budd, Robertson, & Elton, 2004; Degenhardt et al., 2014) with age. Among cocaine users, the aforementioned effects have rarely been studied, although considering the morbidity studies (Bernstein et al., 2007; Chen, Scheier, & Kandel, 1996; Kaye & Darke, 2004; Santos et al., 2012) and the increased all-cause mortality with age

(Hser et al., 2006; Hser et al., 2012; Pavarin, 2008; de la Fuente et al., 2014), an increase of mortality risk from cocaine overdose (acute intoxication) and natural causes with age and time since first cocaine use can be reasonably expected. The effects of age and time since first drug use on mortality can influence each other given their high correlation (Odegard et al., 2007), thus the age effect in users under 45–50 may sometimes be reduced or disappear after adjusting by time since first drug use (Ortí et al., 1996). Disentangling the two effects is important to prioritize and target interventions more effectively, and to assess changes by age in excess mortality of drug users compared with the GP. However, excess mortality has generally been measured using standardized mortality ratios (SMRs), which presents methodological problems (Brugal et al., 2016). For example, the higher all-cause SMR in younger than older drug users (Degenhardt, Bucello et al., 2011) is largely due to very low mortality among young people in the GP (EMCDDA, 2015). To assess healthcare needs, it is also relevant to use absolute measures of excess mortality, which, however, may often yield results opposite to the SMR. The objective of this study was to assess the effect of ageing and time since first heroin/cocaine use on mortality risk from overdose, injuries and natural causes, as well as to quantify age changes in excess mortality from such causes among heroin and cocaine users admitted to drug treatment in Spain during 1997–2008 compared to the GP.

METHODS

- Cohort participants

A retrospective cohort was recruited. The main characteristics can be found elsewhere (Brugal et al., 2016; de la Fuente et al., 2014). It included all heroin (HUs) and cocaine users (CUs) aged 15–49 admitted to outpatient drug dependence treatment in publicly funded facilities during 1997–2007 in Madrid and Barcelona, regardless of any previous admission. Double counting was avoided using a personal identifier. All HUs were using heroin when starting treatment, regardless of whether they were also using cocaine, while CUs were using cocaine but not heroin. The criterion for heroin (or cocaine) use was having requested treatment to control the use of such drug or having used it within 30 days prior to admission.

- Baseline assessment

When treatment began, information was collected on recruitment date, personal identifiers (first name, surname, birthdate and sex), socio-demographic variables (age, education attainment, and current employment), and drug use (lifetime drug injection, current frequency of heroin/cocaine use, and calendar-year of first heroin/cocaine use). Frequency of heroin/cocaine use referred to the last 30 days prior to treatment admission. Missing values were less than 4% for all variables. Data were stored in two databases on separate computers, one containing identifiers, and another the study variables, and later linked with a meaningless code.

- Follow-up

The follow-up ended on 31-12-2008. Vital status, date and underlying cause of death were obtained through record linkage with the general mortality register using the personal identifier. Individuals not identified as dead were considered alive at the end of follow-up. It was estimated that during follow-up 0.2% of the GP aged 15–59 emigrated abroad (INE, 2017). The cause of death initially assigned was the underlying cause coded following the International Classification of Diseases (ICD- (ICD-9 for 1997–1998 and ICD-10 for 1999–2008). However, since in Spain coding of external causes in the general register has limitations, especially for overdose (Santos et al., 2010), in Barcelona the forensic-toxicological register was consulted, assigning the cause from this source to discrepant cases. In this consultation, it was observed that 81% of the deaths included in the general

register under nonspecific codes such as cardiac arrest (427.5, I46), pulmonary oedema (514, 518.4, J81), respiratory failure (799.1, J96), ill-defined conditions (780–799, R00-R74, R76-R99) and toxic effects of alcohol (980.0) were actually overdoses. Since forensic and toxicological consultation to correct the underlying cause of death could not be done in Madrid, the above-mentioned codes were classified as overdose in HU and CU cohorts.

- **Statistical analysis**

Outcomes were deaths from all-causes, overdose, injuries (external causes other than overdose) and natural causes (Randall, Roxburgh, Gibson, & Degenhardt, 2009). ICD overdose codes were selected following recommendations of European institutions (EMCDDA, 2010), validation studies (Santos et al., 2010) and consultation with the Barcelona forensic-toxicological register (Table S1). All analyses were performed separately for CUs and HUs. The time since first heroin (or cocaine) use was calculated as the difference between the calendar-year of death risk assessment (changing during follow-up from baseline to 2008) and the calendar-year of first heroin/cocaine use (fixed for each participant). This means that time since first heroin/cocaine use, as well as age, were analysed as time-varying variables, using the dynamic method of allocation of deaths and persons-year at risk (py) to each of their categories. Crude mortality rates (CRs) for HUs, CUs and the GP living in Madrid and Barcelona during 1997–2008 were calculated and expressed per 100,000 py. Directly age-sex standardized mortality rates (SRs) were also calculated using weights from the 2013 European Standard Population stratified into 5-year age groups.

Independent effects of age and time since first heroin/cocaine use were assessed with the adjusted hazard ratio (aHR), which was estimated using proportional cause-specific hazard models (Competing-risk Cox regression). Time from treatment admission (from treatment admission to death or 31-12-2008) was used as the timescale for the outcome. Results were adjusted by gender, calendar-year of death, city of recruitment, lifetime drug injection, education level, employment, and frequency of cocaine and heroin use, the last four referring to 30 days before treatment admission. A competing risk model was built separately for each cause of death, with deaths from other causes (competing causes) treated as censored observations at the death date and removed from the set of people at risk. The HR expresses how many times higher the instantaneous risk is in a given category compared to the reference among survivors of all competing events to this time point (Putter, Fiocco, & Geskus, 2007). The proportional hazards assumption was checked by smoothed Schoenfeld residuals. All variables fulfilled the assumption, except those entered as time-varying. CRs by 5-year age group were modelled with Joinpoint regression and plotted on an additive and multiplicative scale to observe age changes in absolute and relative excess mortality, respectively, in drug users compared with the GP. Excess mortality was more formally estimated by using age-sex directly standardized rate differences (SRDs) and ratios (SRRs). 95% confidence intervals (95% CIs) of SRR and SRD were estimated by adding the two variances of SRs intervening in SRD and the variance formula for natural logarithm of SRR, respectively (Rothman, Greenland, & Lash, 2008). The proportional contribution of each specific cause of death to all-cause absolute excess mortality was calculated as follows: (specific-cause SRD/all-cause SRD)*100. Analyses were performed with Stata 14.0 (Stata Corporation, College Station, Texas).

RESULTS

- **Baseline characteristics at recruitment**

The study population included 15,305 heroin users (HUs) and 11,905 cocaine users (CUs). About half of participants were aged 40. Most of them were men and had at least secondary education. Many were unemployed. HUs were older than CUs, recruited in an earlier calendar-year, had lower education, higher unemployment, and higher prevalence of lifetime drug injection (48% vs. 7%). 57.7% of HUs had used cocaine in the last 30 days. HUs who used cocaine showed higher frequency and time since first cocaine use than CUs (Table S2). Mean age and time since first cocaine use at baseline were significantly higher among HUs than CUs 33.1 vs. 30.0, and 12.4 vs. 8.9 years, respectively. The mean time since first heroin use at baseline was 12.1 years.

- **Cause-specific mortality by age**

Participants generated 118,902 (HUs) and 65,346 (CUs) py with an average of 6.8 years of follow-up. We recorded 2354 deaths in HUs and 349 in CUs. The most common cause of death at age 15–29 was drug overdose, among both HUs (53.0%) and CUs (49.3%), whereas at age 40–59 it was natural causes (68.1% and 70.1%, respectively). The SRs were higher at age 40–59 than at 15–29 for all causes and natural causes (HUs and CUs), overdose (CUs) and injuries (HUs). However the opposite occurred for overdose (HUs) and injuries (CUs) (Table 1). CRs and proportional mortality by age, gender and more specific causes of death are shown in Tables S3- S16. Infectious/parasitic diseases represented more than 30% of deaths among HUs aged 30–59.

- **Effect of age and time since first drug use on mortality risk from selected causes**

The aHRs from Cox regression by age and time since first heroin and cocaine use are shown in Table 2. The mortality risk from natural causes increased with age among both HUs and CUs, and the same happened with injuries among HUs. However, the fatal overdose risk remained stable with age among HUs and appeared to increase among CUs, albeit without reaching statistical significance.

Mortality risk from natural causes increased with time since first heroin use, while that from overdose decreased. Thus, fatal overdose risk in HUs with less than 10 years of heroin use was significantly higher than in former HUs (aHR < 5 = 1.6 and aHR 5- 9 = 1.2). Statistically significant effects of time since first cocaine use on cause-specific mortality risk among CUs or HUs were not identified, although fatal overdose risk seemed lower in CUs with <5 years of use (Table 2).

- **Excess mortality in drug users compared to the general population by age**

An increase in absolute excess mortality from all causes with age can be observed by focusing on the difference in CRs between drug users (HUs or CUs) and the GP in the graph with the additive scale, while a decrease in relative excess mortality with age can be observed by focusing on the same difference in the graph with the multiplicative (logarithmic) scale (Fig. 1). Absolute and relative excess mortality of HUs and CUs compared to the GP by age group and cause of death using SRs is shown in Table 3. In HUs the all-cause SRR was much higher at age 15–29 than 40–59 (26.6 vs. 8.3), while the opposite occurred with SRD (814 vs. 2134 deaths/ 100,000 person-years). In CUs the pattern was similar, although the age-group disparity appeared less pronounced when using SRR (7.9 at age 15–29 vs. 4.2 at age 40–59) than when using SRD (221 vs. 927 deaths/100,000 person-years). Considering the cause of death, the SRD tends to increase with age, except for overdose (HUs) and injuries (CUs). However, the SRR from overdose and natural causes

seems to decrease with age among HUs and to increase among CUs, whereas the opposite occurs with SRR from injuries. Among HUs, the main contributing causes to absolute excess mortality from all causes were overdose at age 15–29 (66%), and natural causes at ages 30–39 (54%) and 40–59 (63%), while among CUs they were injuries at age 15–29 (51%), overdose and injuries at age 30–39 (40% and 40%), and natural causes at age 40–59 (74%) (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

- **Main findings**

Among HUs, mortality risk from natural causes and injuries increased with age, and the risk from natural causes also increased with time since first of heroin use. Fatal overdose risk decreased with time since first heroin use, with the highest risk found in people using heroin for <5 years. Among CUs, natural mortality increased with age, while fatal overdose increased with age and time since first cocaine use. Fatal overdose and injuries remained very high at age 40–59 among both HUs and CUs. Absolute excess mortality from all and natural causes increased with age in both HUs and CUs, whereas the opposite occurred with relative excess mortality.

- **The effect of age and time since first heroin use on mortality in heroin users**

Our findings suggest that among HUs mortality risk from natural causes increases with time since first heroin use and especially with age. The age effect has consistently been identified elsewhere (Brugal et al., 2005; Clausen et al., 2009; EMCDDA, 2015; Larney et al., 2015; Pierce et al., 2015), while the length effect has been identified in some studies (Ortí et al., 1996; Brugal et al., 2005), but not others (Langendam, van Brussel, Coutinho, & van Ameijden, 2001; Evans et al., 2012), probably due to low statistical power. Such effects are compatible with increased prevalence of somatic comorbidities (i.e., infections, hepatic and circulatory diseases) and poorer physical health with increasing age or time since first use due to long exposure to multiple risk factors (Hser, Hoffman, Grella, & Anglin, 2001; Hser et al., 2012; Larney et al., 2015; Rosen et al., 2008, 2011). This is also reflected in an increase in all-cause mortality with increasing age or time since first use (Oppenheimer, Tobutt, Taylor, & Andrew, 1994; Ortí et al., 1996; Bartu et al., 2004; Brugal et al., 2005; Clausen et al., 2009; Langendam et al., 2001; Odegard et al., 2007; Quan et al., 2007; van Haastrecht et al., 1996; Beynon, McVeigh, Hurst, & Marr, 2010; Cousins et al., 2016; Degenhardt et al., 2014; Larney et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2013; Merrall et al., 2012; Pierce et al., 2015). Findings also suggest that fatal overdose risk changes little with age and continues to be very high at relatively old ages (i.e., 595 deaths/ 100,000 py at age 40–59). Fatal overdose risk measured by the SR decreased with age, but not after adjusting for time since first heroin use, because this variable has an opposite effect. Thus, the aHR for <5 compared to 10 years of use was 1.6. Most studies have not found a decreasing fatal overdose risk with age (Bartu et al., 2004; Bird et al., 2003; Buster et al., 2002; Clausen et al., 2009; Merrall et al., 2012; Odegard et al., 2007; Pierce et al., 2015), but some do (Copeland et al., 2004; Cousins et al., 2011; Larney et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2013). Moreover, most non-fatal overdose studies have found a greater risk in younger than older opioid users (Bergenstrom et al., 2008; Coffin et al., 2007; Horyniak et al., 2013; Kerr et al., 2007; Kinner et al., 2012; Seal et al., 2001; Bretteville-Jensen, Lillehagen, Gjersing, & Andreas, 2015). Regarding time since first heroin use, a fatal overdose study found a higher risk in long-term users (Odegard et al., 2007), while non-fatal overdose studies have generally found higher risk in short-term users (Powis et al., 1999; Stewart, Gossop, & Marsden, 2002; Bazazi et al., 2015; Brugal et al., 2002), although some do not (Darke et al., 2009; Uuskula et al., 2015). Admitting that non-fatal overdose risk declines with age, the persistence of a high fatal overdose risk among older heroin users and its low decline with age could be explained

primarily by an increased overdose lethality at older ages due mainly to increased disease burden (i.e., hepatic disease) (Stoove et al., 2009; Warner-Smith et al., 2001; Merrall et al., 2012). The higher fatal overdose risk in short-term heroin users could be explained by less skills and experience to avoid overdose, lower opioid tolerance, lower exposure to harm reduction interventions (i.e., OST), higher frequency of heroin use or overdose risk factors (i.e., concurrent use of opioids and other depressants, use of injecting route) compared to long-term users (Coffin et al., 2007; Galea et al., 2006; Larney et al., 2015). The mortality risk from injuries (unintentional injuries, suicide or homicide) increased with ageing and remained very high at age 40–59 among HUs (217 deaths/100,000 py). The reasons are unclear, although psychiatric comorbidities, prolonged opioid-addicted life-style and small protective effect of OST may predispose to traumatic deaths (Clausen et al., 2009; Darke et al., 2009). An increase or lack of decline in such risk with age has been also found elsewhere (Clausen et al., 2009; Larney et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2013; Merrall et al., 2012; Pierce et al., 2015), but not in all studies (Copeland et al., 2004; Degenhardt et al., 2014). Moreover, the population risk of drug-related injuries decreased after age 44 in a cross-sectional study (Webb et al., 2003). The variable age at first use could have been entered into the multivariate model instead of time since first use (since the two variables are highly correlated they cannot be assessed together). When time since first use was replaced by age at first use, the results were quite consistent (i.e., the mortality risk from natural causes increases with increasing time since first heroin use, while such risk increases with decreasing age at first heroin use) However, it should be emphasized that an increased risk of fatal overdose in those starting heroin use earlier (<18 years or <22 years) was not shown).

- **The effect of age and time since first cocaine use on mortality in cocaine users**

Mortality risk from natural causes significantly increased with age, especially at age 40–59. Findings also suggest that fatal overdose risk could increase with age and time since first cocaine use. Although the effects of such variables on cause-specific mortality have rarely been studied among CUs, some studies have found increases in all-cause mortality risk with age (Hser et al., 2006; Hser et al., 2012; Pavarin, 2008; de la Fuente et al., 2014) and increases in risk of non-fatal overdose or cocaine-related physical problems with age or time since first cocaine use (Chen et al., 1996; Kaye & Drake, 2004; Bernstein et al., 2007; Santos et al., 2012). However, it should be noted that diagnosing acute cocaine intoxications (overdoses) is not easy (Stephens, Jentzen, Karch, Wetli, & Mash, 2004; Graham & Hanzlick, 2008), so they may be poorly classified in mortality statistics. The increases in mortality risk from overdose or natural causes could be due to pre-existing health problems (i.e., atherosclerosis, heart disease), whose prevalence increases with age and may be exacerbated by cocaine use (Beynon, 2009; Galea et al., 2006). Cocaine may have timelagged cumulative effects, especially on the circulatory system, triggering acute problems when a threshold is reached (Bernstein et al., 2007; Chen et al., 1996). Also, age-related changes in drug pharmacokinetics may lead to higher blood cocaine concentration or higher sensitivity to cocaine (Lynskey, Day, & Hall, 2003). Mortality risk from injuries was high, especially before age 40. The association of cocaine use with non-fatal and fatal unintentional or intentional injuries among young adults has been reported in multiple studies (Chermack & Blow, 2002; Doherty, Robertson, Green, Fothergill, & Ensminger, 2012; Macdonald et al., 2003; Marzuk et al., 1995; Merrall et al., 2012; Murray et al., 2008; Pavarin et al., 2011; Pennay et al., 2016; Silverman, Raj, Mucci, & Hathaway, 2001; Stoduto, Mann, Ialomiteanu, Wickens, & Brands, 2012; Walton et al., 2009).

- **Age differences in excess mortality of heroin and cocaine users**

Most previous studies on age disparity in excess mortality in HUs or drug injectors have used only relative indicators of excess mortality like standardized mortality ratios (SMRs) (Degenhardt, Bucello et al., 2011; Nambiar et al., 2015; Oppenheimer et al., 1994; Pierce et

al., 2015), and have usually found higher all-cause SMRs in younger participants (Degenhardt, Bucello et al., 2011; EMCDDA, 2015; Nambiar et al., 2015; Oppenheimer et al., 1994). There are few studies of this subject among CUs. In our study disparity indicators on an absolute (SRD) or relative (SRR) scale were used to assess age-group disparities in excess mortality among HUs and CUs compared to the GP. It is known that one might arrive at opposite conclusions, depending on which disparity measure (absolute or relative) was chosen (King, Harper, & Young, 2012; Brugal et al., 2016). Thus, in our study SRD from all and natural causes increased with age in both HUs and CUs, whereas the opposite occurred with SRR. The contradiction is only apparent because this means a stronger association between being HU or CU and mortality at younger ages and yet a greater impact of such conditions on population mortality at older ages. SRR is higher in young drug users because they would engage in harmful behaviours with the same or higher frequency than older users, and dying young is a rare event in the GP in wealthy countries. With ageing, the mortality risk increases in both drug users and the GP due to organic deterioration, resulting in a decreased SRR (relative excess mortality) but an increased SRD (absolute excess mortality). This latter is mainly due to increased SRD from natural causes (i.e., infectious/parasitic diseases, liver diseases, cancer) among older users, although the persistently high SRDs from overdose (HUs and CUs) and injuries (HUs) also contributed. The important contribution of natural causes, especially infectious/ parasitic and liver diseases, to excess mortality in older HUs or drug injectors has been reported in numerous studies (Alejos et al., 2016; Beynon et al., 2010; EMCDDA, 2015; Larney et al., 2015; Pierce et al., 2015). A substantial increase in excess mortality (SRD and SRR) from injuries with age was observed in our HU cohort, which is relevant to public health practice because these are clearly preventable causes. Such a finding has rarely been reported, although one study also found an increase in homicide SMR with age (Degenhardt et al., 2014). The huge increase in all-cause SRD with ageing among CUs was mainly due to natural causes, although until age 39 external causes also contributed. Changes by age in excess mortality from overdose are difficult to interpret and are probably attributable to differences in the allocation of cause of death between the cohort and GP.

- **Strengths and limitations**

This is perhaps the first study to calculate age disparity in excess mortality of HUs and CUs compared to the GP using both absolute and relative disparity measures. It is also one of the first to assess mortality risk by age or time since first cocaine use among cocaine users, after excluding subjects who also used heroin. An appropriate methodology has been used to analyse cause-specific mortality and to disentangle the effects of age and time since first drug use (competing risk Cox regression). Our study also has limitations. First, there was no assessment of drug use or injecting status during follow-up. This could bias the results if behavioural changes (i.e., cessation of opioid use) were differential by age. Valid data on drug use patterns which could explain age disparities in mortality (i.e., recent drug injection, benzodiazepines or alcohol use, exposure to harm reduction, etc.) were not available. There may be some misclassification of cause of death, especially for overdose. Overdoses in Spain are almost always initially certified as non-specific deaths (e.g., pulmonary oedema). These causes often remain as definitive in the general mortality register because they are not changed based on forensic and toxicological data (Santos et al., 2012). To improve the classification, in Barcelona the forensic registry was consulted, and codes in the general register for HUs and CUs were corrected in accordance with the new data. As mentioned above, the vast majority of deaths classified under nonspecific codes in the general register were actually overdoses, so in the Madrid cohort, for which forensic consultation could not be performed, deaths under these codes were classified as overdoses. Finally, 55.7% of deaths classified as overdoses in the drug users' cohort corresponded to nonspecific ICD codes such as ill-defined conditions (41.0%), pulmonary oedema (8.6%), cardiac arrest

(3.2%), and respiratory failure (2.9%). Some misclassification of drug use patterns at baseline may occur due to recall biases, socially desirable responses or limitations of treatment registers. Finally, the statistical power remains low for less common mortality causes (i.e., injuries).

- **Implications for policy and practice**

In 1997–2008 in Spain (and probably in other developed countries), a substantial part of the absolute excess mortality in HUs and CUs compared to the GP appears at a fairly advanced age. Thus, in our study HUs and CUs aged 40 or more accounted for 46.9% and 56.6%, respectively, of all the absolute excess mortality of HUs and CUs of 15–59 years. Although excess mortality is largely due to chronic diseases caused by harmful behaviours initiated long before, these drug users remain at high risk of mortality from acute short-term preventable problems such as overdose or injuries after age 40. Consequently, a high level of harm reduction and healthcare services (i.e., OST, take-home naloxone, HIV and hepatitis C diagnosis and treatment, etc.) in older drug users should be maintained (Degenhardt et al., 2014; Larney et al., 2015). Social support services are also needed because these people usually have limited family support. Also, healthcare professionals should be prepared to deal with heroin and cocaine problems in users at relatively advanced ages.

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